

Potential of Critical Raw Materials in Closed Finnish Mine Waste Sites: A Preliminary Review

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ABSTRACT

The increasing demand for raw materials has led to a shift in focus towards extractive waste sites as potential sources of secondary resources. The Future Availability of Secondary Raw Materials (FutuRaM) project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme, is investigating secondary raw materials in Europe. The FutuRaM knowledge base is poised to become a valuable source on the availability and recoverability of secondary raw materials within the European Union, with a special focus on critical raw materials. Based on the preliminary data from the 24 largest closed metal mine sites in Finland, these sites may contain considerable amounts of cobalt (Co) (22,300 tonnes), copper (Cu) (103,400 tonnes), and nickel (Ni) (92,600 tonnes). Most of these metals are expected to be found in the assessed 20 tailings sites, with waste amounts ranging from 0.4 to 20 Mt and totalling around 131 Mt. To a lesser extent metals could be hosted by the eight investigated waste rock sites, with waste amounts ranging from 0.3 to 5.5 Mt and totalling around 18 Mt. However, the existing data is uncertain due to the limited number of samples from most of the sites, inadequate analysis methods and indirect estimations of the amount of waste. Furthermore, the relatively low concentrations of these raw materials, commonly ranging from 0.002 to 0.2%, compared to conventional ore grades, pose significant challenges in beneficiation and, thus, eventually economic remining of extractive wastes in Finland. This study emphasizes the potential of the closed Finnish extractive waste sites as sources of critical raw materials, while concurrently highlighting the difficulties associated with resource estimation and feasible valorization. A holistic approach to extractive waste management is needed, as remining critical raw materials seldom achieves economic viability alone. Remining requires consideration of all potentially viable solutions. This means that the focus should be on comprehensively evaluating different valorization possibilities for the extractive waste, alongside environmental impacts and social responsibility.

Key Words: secondary resources, tailings, remining, circular economy, critical minerals

INTRODUCTION

In the European Union (EU), critical raw materials (CRMs) are defined as raw materials that are crucial to the European economy and possess a high risk associated with their supply. The European Commission (EC) has released a list of CRMs that is regularly reviewed and updated to reflect changes related to markets and technological development. The fifth update of the list, including 34 CRMs, was published in 2023 (EC, 2023). The need for certain CRMs is increasing, as they are necessary for clean technologies such as solar panels, wind turbines, electric vehicles, and more. The growing concern regarding the availability of CRMs has shifted attention towards extractive waste sites as potential sources of secondary resources. For example, the Raw Materials Act states that at least 15% of the EU's annual consumption should come from recycling by 2030 (EC, 2024). To work towards this, EU countries and private operators should investigate the potential for recovery of CRMs from extractive waste, and preferably classify the resources based on the United Nations Framework Classification for Resources (UNFC). UNFC is a dynamic, principle-based classification system for the transparent communication of the availability of mineral and energy resources, which forms the basis of the United Nations Resource Management System (UNRMS). It aims to take a holistic view of resource availability by integrating

socio-economic, environmental, and technical factors. It is meant to provide authorities and industry stakeholders with robust data for informed decision-making.

The FutuRaM project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme, was established to develop a Secondary Raw Materials knowledge base on the availability and recoverability of secondary raw materials (2RMs) within the EU, with a special focus on CRMs (FutuRaM, 2024). The aim of the project, which is active from 2022 through to 2026, is to enable fact-based decision making for the recovery and use of 2RMs within and outside the EU. It will also establish a methodology, reporting structure, and guidance to improve the raw materials knowledge base up to 2050.

In Finland, around 100 Mt of extractive waste is being produced annually, which comprises 74% of the total amount of all waste streams. Since the 16th century, over 1,100 Mt of waste rock has been excavated, of which most, around 96% during the last 50 years, and half during the last decade. Since the introduction of the flotation processing method in Finland in 1911, around 500 Mt of tailings have been produced (Puustinen, 2003). As part of the FutuRaM project, existing extractive waste data from closed mine sites have been gathered by the Geological Survey of Finland (GTK) to an extractive waste database (GTK, 2024). This study presents preliminary data and results regarding the closed Finnish extractive waste sites as a source of secondary CRMs, concentrating on Co, Cu and Ni.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The extractive waste data have been primarily sourced from the archives of GTK, including data produced in past projects and publications related to closed mine sites (Table 1). The data have been compiled and stored in the METSO database of GTK (GTK 2024), which currently serves as a centralized repository for data related to extractive wastes as potential secondary resource in Finland. For the purpose of this study, the focus has been narrowed to closed mine sites, and the CRMs to Co, Cu and Ni. These CRMs were selected due to their industrial importance and the common occurrence in the Finnish extractive waste.

Table 1. The closed Finnish mine sites included in this study

Mine	Active	Tailings (Mt)	Waste rock (Mt)
Pyhäsalmi	1962–2022	20.0	-
Hitura	1970–2013	15.0	5.5
Luikonlahti	1968–2020	14.3	-
Vihanti	1954–1992	13.7	-
Otanmäki	1953–1985	11.8	-
Rautuvaara	1962–1996	9.5	-
Kotalahti	1959–1987	9.4	-
Vuonos	1972–1985	9.0	4.6
Enonkoski	1986–1994	6.6	-
Hammaslahti	1971–1986	5.3	2.3
Virtasalmi	1966–1984	4.2	0.5
Raajärvi	1964–1975	2.9	-
Ylöjärvi	1943–1966	2.8	-
Aijala	1949–1974	2.0	-
Haveri	1942–1961	1.4	-
Orijärvi	1758–1955	1.0	-
Outokumpu	1910–1989	1.0	-
Mätäsvaara	1940–1947	1.0	-
Kylmäkoski	1971–1974	0.7	-
Makola	1941–1954	0.4	-
Saattopora	1988–1995	-	3.6
Rämepuro	2012–2017	-	0.9
Kangasjärvi	1984–1986	-	0.7
Pahtavuoma	1974–1995	-	0.3

In this study, the tonnages of the CRMs Co, Cu and Ni have been calculated based on historical extraction and ore processing data (amount of waste), and available concentration data originating mainly from small-scale environmental investigations conducted by GTK during the last decades. It is important to note that the data presented in this study is preliminary. The values and findings are subject to change as further processing and refinement of the data are conducted and new investigations are being made.

The extractive waste sites included in this study (Table 1, Figure 1) comprise the most major closed mine sites in Finland, with some minor exclusions. All the closed Finnish tailings sites have been included, excluding the tailings (0.9 Mt) of the Korsnäs Pb mine, which does not contain significant concentrations of Co, Cu or Ni.

Figure 1. Locations of the closed Finnish mine sites included in this study

The waste rock sites presented in this study include all the closed Finnish mine sites with ≥ 0.3 Mt of waste rock. Of the 24 mine sites, 20 contained tailings and eight contained waste rock. The primary emphasis of this study was on the tailings data, which is presented in more detail. The tailings sites presented in this study are surface impoundments, which contain most of the tailings' mass. Some minor amounts can be backfilled to the underground mines. At many of the major closed mine sites, the amount of waste rock was less significant compared with tailings, and/or less data was available. This was because several of the significant closed mines were underground operations, which resulted in lesser amounts of waste rock. Some of the selected mine sites did not have tailings, as the ore was transported to other mine sites for processing e.g., ore from Saattopora and Pahtavuoma mines to Rautuvaara, and ore from Kangasjärvi to Pyhäsalmi. Several similar smaller scale mine sites exist in Finland, containing only waste rock, but they are probably insignificant regarding CRM remaining potential. The largest waste rock piles are located at the currently active mine sites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to the existing data from the investigated closed extractive waste sites in Finland, the sites may contain considerable amounts of Co (22,300 tonnes), Cu (103,400 tonnes), and Ni (92,600 tonnes). Most of these CRMs, around 21,500 t of Co, 90,200 t of Cu and 74,600 t of Ni, are found in the 20 tailings sites, with waste amounts ranging from 0.4 to 20 Mt and totalling around 131 Mt (Table 2). Lesser amounts, around 800 t of Co, 13,200 t of Cu and 18,000 t of Ni, are found in the eight waste rock sites, with waste amounts ranging from 0.3 to 5.5 Mt and totalling around 18 Mt.

Despite the seemingly significant amounts of CRMs in closed Finnish extractive waste facilities, the preliminary assessment has highlighted notable challenges. For one thing, at most of the extractive waste sites, the available data is originating from smaller scale environmental studies, which is highly uncertain for estimating resource quantities due to the limited number of samples and lacking quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC). Therefore, there is also little knowledge regarding the heterogeneity and continuity of potential recoverable grade values in these waste materials. Furthermore, the assay method in environmental studies has often been aqua regia extraction, instead of measuring the total concentrations, which would be the preferred method in resource potential studies to screen the potential of all critical elements. The amount of the wastes have also not been based on direct evidence but assessed based on literature and old processing data, and no density data is available.

It should be highlighted that the concept of remaining extractive waste is not a recent development. In Finland, thorough resource potential studies, consisting of taking and analyzing hundreds of drilled samples, have been carried out already in the early 1980s at the Aijala, Haveri, Orijärvi, and Kotalahti tailings sites. These studies concluded that remaining the wastes was not a feasible option at the time. However, currently there is a growing interest in a broader range of elements and minerals, coupled with advancements in ore processing methods than in the 1980s.

The extraction of Co, Cu, and Ni could be challenging due to their apparent low concentrations, which ranged between 0.002% and 0.2% (Table 2), and are much lower than conventional ore grades. Furthermore, in the case of tailings, the easier processable fraction of the valuable elements might have already been recovered in the first processing round. For example, at the Hitura tailings site, most of the calculated 32,090 t of Ni might be included in the less easily processable silicates (Heikkinen & Räsänen 2008). In general, there is a little knowledge about the minerals that host the CRMs at these extractive waste sites. Further site characterization, systematic sampling, and additional mineralogical work, in coordination with newer R&D and re-processing technologies would be beneficial in addressing these issues.

Table 2. Amount of tailings, and concentrations (%) and amounts (t) of Co, Cu and Ni at the selected closed tailings sites in Finland

Mine	Active	Tailings (Mt)*	Co (%)	Co (t)	Cu (%)	Cu (t)	Ni (%)	Ni (t)	Notes**
Pyhäsalmi	1962–2022	20.0	0–0.01	550	0.06–0.1	15500	0–0.002	120	Composition data from production statistics and minor sampling. Several tailings ponds with variable material.
Hitura	1970–2013	15.0			0.1	14760	0.2	32090	Sampling and analysis data not available
Luikonlahti	1968–2020	14.3	0.04–0.6	8670	0.03–0.2	8080	0.04–0.2	7450	Sampling and analysis data not available, three tailings types in the largest pond, a separate Co-Ni pond
Vihanti	1954–1992	13.7			0.1	10960			Production statistics, estimation from 1981
Otanmäki	1953–1985	9.8	0.02	1960	0.01	980	0.02	1960	Sampling and analysis data not available
Rautuvaara	1962–1996	9.5	0.01–0.02	1170	0.1	1400	0.004–0.02	750	Sampling by drilling in 2006; 53 samples from 13 drill cores by GTK. Analyses by Aqua Regia extraction. Processed ore from various deposits.
Kotalahti	1959–1987	9.4	0.003	280	0.03	3100	0.06	5730	Sampling and analysis data not available
Vuonos	1972–1985	9.0	0.07	6300	0.2	17100	0.1	9000	Sampling and analysis data not available
Enonkoski	1986–1994	6.6	0.01	660	0.06	3960	0.2	15180	Sampling and analysis data not available
Hammaslahti	1971–1986	5.3	0.01	290	0.1	4040	0.002	80	Sampling and analysis data not available
Virtasalmi	1966–1984	4.2	0.05	210	0.03	1300	0.01	420	Sampling and analysis data not available
Raajärvi	1964–1975	2.9	0.01	380	0.02	520	0.01	380	Sampling and analysis data not available
Ylöjärvi	1943–1966	2.8	0.01	140	0.02	590			Sampling by drilling in early 1980's; 244 samples from 26 cores obtained with Auger type coring device. AAS-method with HNO ₃ solution; Cu, Zn, Co, Pb, Ag, W, Fe
Aijala	1949–1974	2.0			0.1	2380			Sampling by drilling in early 1980's; 249 samples from 28 cores obtained with Auger type coring device. AAS-method with HNO ₃ solution; Cu, Zn, Ni, Co, Pb, Ag, Fe, Au
Haveri	1942–1961	1.4	0.01	200	0.1	1310	0.01	180	Sampling by drilling in early 1980's; 1201 samples from 165 drill cores, auger type of sampling. AAS-method with HNO ₃ solution; Cu, Zn, Ni, Co, Pb, Ag, Fe, S. Later further sampling from 40 drill cores 3 test pits
Orijärvi	1758–1955	1.0	0.003	30	0.2	1800			Sampling by drilling in early 1980's; 112 samples from 13 drill cores, auger drilling device. AAS-method with HNO ₃ solution; Cu, Zn, Ni, Co, Pb, Ag, Fe, S
Outokumpu	1910–1989	1.0	0.06	600	0.14	1430			Sampling and analysis data not available
Mätäsvaara	1940–1947	1.0			0.03	290			Sampling and analysis data not available, 5 samples for beneficiation studies in 1976
Kylmäkoski	1971–1974	0.7	0.01	70	0.04	280	0.1	590	Sampling and analysis data not available
Makola	1941–1954	0.4			0.1	420	0.17	630	Production statistics, mean values from 1943/1944
			Total t	21510		90200		74560	

* All amount estimations based on literature data

** Sampling and analysis data not available: data from sporadic samples often related to environmental studies by GTK

The observed shortages in extractive waste data quality have implications in making meaningful secondary CRM assessments. In the future, UNFC will provide a standardized framework for comparing raw materials projects across the spectrum from exploration to extraction, processing, and recycling in Europe. The UNFC classification code is based on a three-dimensional framework, with category definitions or the three-dimensional axes serving as its foundational components (Figure 2, UNECE 2019). These categories/axes represent the three core criteria: environmental-socio-economic viability (E-axis), technical feasibility (F-axis), and the level of confidence (G-axis). Progressing along each axis, uncertainty is reduced, moving from the worst rating of 4 down to the best rating of 1. Basically, projects with code numbers of E1F1G1-3 can be classified as viable projects either in production or in near-production without technical or non-technical contingencies or block factors. In general, most of the Finnish extractive waste sites as sources of secondary CRMs would fall under the highest code numbers with high uncertainties.

Figure 2. The UNFC classification system is based on a three-dimensional framework, with category definitions of environmental-socio-economic viability (E-axis), technical feasibility (F-axis), and the level of confidence (G-axis). Progressing along each axis, uncertainty is reduced, moving from the worst rating of 4 down to the best rating of 1. Figure from UNECE (2019).

So far in Finland, only one site, the Otanmäki tailings facility, has been recently assessed in more detail and classified according to the UNFC system. The closed Otanmäki Fe-V mine, which was first owned by Otanmäki Oy and later by Rautaruukki Oy, is currently owned and developed by Otanmäki Mine Oy. During the active years of 1953–1985, around 25.5 Mt of ore was extracted, and the produced 9.8 Mt of tailings were deposited in a 145 hectare pond (Otanmäki Mine Oy 2024). However, the Otanmäki Mine Oy is not interested in the recovery of the 1960 t of Co, 980 t of Cu and 1960 t of Ni presented in Table 2, as the beneficiation of these CRMs has not been proved feasible. Instead, the company is planning to remine the approximate 16% of ilmenite (FeTiO_3) in the tailings. According to the UNFC system, the Otanmäki ilmenite project has been classified as E2F2G2, a potentially viable project. The Otanmäki tailings facility is a case site for the FutuRaM project and will serve as a documented example for future remining projects, along with other guidance created in the project.

As can be observed from the Otanmäki case and the low metal grades in extractive wastes in general, concentrating only on CRM metals might not be economically feasible. Kinnunen et al. (2022) point out, that a holistic extractive waste management approach with a comprehensive evaluation of valorization possibilities of extractive waste should be made to achieve economically viable solutions. In addition to concentrating on the metals, the valorization assessment should also include utilization of bulk minerals e.g., in cement production, CO₂ capture, or upscaling the materials to more valuable products, like ceramics. In some cases, the insufficiently closed extractive waste facility may require rehabilitation and/or long-term monitoring with significant costs anyway, which might enhance the overall feasibility of a remining project as part of the environmental solution. In any case, the environmental impacts of remining a historic site and the management of newly generated waste, alongside social responsibility issues, should be assessed in detail as part of the holistic approach.

Before a holistic extractive waste management and valorization assessment can be made in Finland, more detailed information is needed about the amount and composition of the waste materials at the closed Finnish mine sites. As the existing information is lacking and interest in the potential of extractive wastes as potential sources for secondary resources is high, the EU and the Finnish government have invested in a thorough investigation programme of the old extractive waste sites. In two separate GTK involved projects, 12–17 potentially interesting, closed mine sites will be assessed during 2024–2025. The preliminary review of CRM potential and guidance documents created in the FutuRaM project will serve as a solid base to select the sites to be investigated and to design the field work.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the preliminary review, the closed Finnish extractive waste sites, especially tailings facilities, offer potential as secondary sources of CRMs. However, notable uncertainties were observed concerning the data quality, which makes reliable resource classification challenging. Furthermore, as the observed CRM metal grades are relatively low, a holistic approach should be used when assessing the remining potential of a closed extractive waste site and to achieve economically viable solutions. This means that the focus should be on comprehensively evaluating different valorization possibilities for the extractive waste, alongside environmental impacts and social responsibility. Data quality and the ability to make holistic extractive waste management assessments will be enhanced in the near future as the resource potential of several closed Finnish extractive waste sites is being assessed in EU and government-funded projects. The preliminary review and guidance created in the FutuRaM project will be used to steer the new projects.

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